

Smart Helmet using IoT

P. Brahmendra S. Prakash

Abstract: The goal of the adroit guarded top is to give a systems and mechanical social affair to recognizing and revealing mishaps. Sensors, and passed on enrolling frameworks are used for building the structure. The occurrence conspicuous evidence framework gives the accelerometer respects to the processor which dependably screens for unusual combinations. Right when a disaster occurs, the related nuances are sent to the emergency contacts by utilizing cloud based assistance. The vehicle area is acquired by utilizing the general masterminding structure. The framework guarantees a reliable and brisk development of data identifying with the episode constantly and up dated to cloud which are gotten to by IOT. In this way, by utilizing the unavoidable framework which is a striking part for the watchful urban zones, a mind blowing protective top for calamity ID is created.

Keywords: Disaster Detection, Alcohol Detection, Internet of Things, IR sensor and Smart Helmet.

I. INTRODUCTION

The bike accidents are extending a little bit at a time and lead to the loss of different lives. By using defensive top can lessen the probability of bike accidents. By surveying these days 1.2 million people are losing their critical lives in road accidents. In regular day to day existence, there are various setbacks occurring for which some arrangement must be found when the episode happens. The demise rate isn't diminishing in any event, when the medical clinics are giving emergency vehicle administrations. Thus, to beat every one of these issues, there are two significant criteria checked by keen protective cap before the bicycle begins. It is set in the cap. At the point when the individual is profoundly expended the liquor, the gas sensor will detect the riders inhale to distinguish the measure of liquor content. Third, when an individual meets with a mishap, in the event that the mishap is major, at that point the sensor will distinguish the bicycle's condition and the individual's area will be sent to close by emergency clinics through GPS to the primary server of the medical clinic. On the off chance that the mishap is minor, there is a catch present in the bicycle ought to be squeezed by the individual. This underwear that the individual isn't harmed and the bicycle will begin.

II. RELATED WORK

Dr. Himadri Nath Saha proposes an instrument by using the parameters, for instance, flex sensor, breathe in analyzer, influence sensor, Bluetooth for disaster recognizable proof and shows how huge the alert by using SVM. Ms. Rekha. M, Ms. Bharathi.

Revised Manuscript Received on February 06, 2020.

P. Brahmendra, UG Student, Institute of Electronics and Communication, Saveetha School of Engineering, SIMATS, Thandalam, Chennai, India.

Dr. S. Prakash, Institute of Electronics and Communication, Saveetha School of Engineering, SIMATS, Thandalam, Chennai, India.

K proposes the advancement perceives proportion of alcohol in blood in case the purpose of imprisonment is over quite far, by then the vehicle won't move. P. Tharangai Thamil, S.Vanitha proposes to pick the divulgence of rash driving utilizing accelerometer and sensors. Amrutha Madhusan proposes the structure which targets decreasing the loss of individual's lives in street occurrences and performs such assignments as difficulty perceiving and sending of the zone to the close to restorative focus. Prabha experience gives an accelerometer which is utilized in a vehicle upsetting application so the unsafe driving can be perceived. Aboli Ravindra Wakure proposes the framework with the accelerometer sensor for vehicle security structure. Mohd Khairul Afiq Mohd Rasli exhibited that everyone should wear the top and Seat belt along these lines, it decreases the passing rate. In case the Person crosses quite far, by then the caution will be given to the rider. Aravinda B proposed a reaction for the episode issue is admonishing the driver about the contrary side coming vehicle. Jesudoss et al proposed a cloud-based course of action for social security data structures. This work leaves behind a protected system to putting data in an affirmed manner.

III. EXSISTING SYSTEM

In the present structure individuals have been using the top only for external prosperity. There is no neutralizing activity for alcohol use.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed framework we can screen likewise as control security status of the individual who wears the guarded top. The flourishing status of top is top tier and the essential move to be made through information is obliged by IOT.

V. MODULES

1. ARDUINO UNO (2)
2. ACCELEROMETER
3. TOUCH SENSOR (IR SENSOR)
4. VIBRATION SENSOR
5. GAS SENSOR
6. RELAY

DESCRIPTION:

ARDUINO UNO (2):

Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board reliant on the ATmega328P (datasheet). It has 14 modernized information/yield pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM yields), 6 away from of data, a 16 MHz quartz noteworthy stone, a USB partnership, a force jack, an ICSP header and a reset catch. It contains everything expected to help the microcontroller; on a very basic level assistant it to a PC with a USB affiliation or force it with an AC-to-DC connector or battery to start.

Smart Helmet using IoT

You can tinker with your UNO without anguishing basically over achieving something wrongly, most mad result reasonable you can swap the chip for a few dollars and start again.

ACCELEROMETER:

The ADXL335 is genuinely, feeble, low force, all out 3-center accelerometer with signal framed voltage yields. The thing gauges accusing of a base full-scale level of ± 3 g. It can check the static quickening gravity in tilt seeing applications, similarly as incredible reviving happening as expected thinking about headway, stifle, or vibration. The customer picks the transmission farthest reaches of the accelerometer using the CX, CY, and CZ capacitors at the XOUT, YOUT, and ZOUT pins. Information move limits can be picked to suit the application, with a level of 0.5 Hz to 1600 Hz for X and Y tomahawks, and a level of 0.5 Hz to 550 Hz for the Z turn. The ADXL335 is available in a little, low profile, 4 mm $\times$ 4 mm $\times$ 1.45 mm, 16-lead, plastic lead graph chip scale package(LFCSP_LQ).

TOUCH SENSOR (IR SENSOR):

An infrared sensor is an electronic contraption that radiates in order to recognize a couple of bits of the earth. An IR sensor can check the sparkle of a thing similarly as sees the progression. All around in the infrared range, the total of the articles transmits a type of warm radiations. These sorts of radiations are vague to our eyes that can be seen by an infrared sensor. The maker is only an IR LED (Light Emitting Diode) and the locator is basically an IR photodiode which is sensitive to IR light of a close to wavelength as that transmitted by the IR LED. Absolutely when IR light falls on the photodiode, the securities and these yield voltages, change concerning the size of the IR light got.

VIBRATION SENSOR:

Vibration Sensor (SW-420) is a high affectability non-directional vibration sensor. Precisely when the module is persevering through, the circuit is turned on and the yield is high. Right when the improvement or vibration happens, the circuit will be quickly kept and yield low. Simultaneously, you can in like way change the affectability as showed by your very own unique needs. The SW-420 is another vibration switch that opens when vibration is seen and closes when there is no vibration.

GAS SENSOR:

Delicate material of MQ-2 gas sensor is SnO₂, which with lower conductivity in clean air. Right when the objective burnable gas exist, The sensor's conductivity is reliably higher close to the gas fixation rising. You should utilize key electro circuit, Convert change of conductivity to see posted notification of gas fixation. MQ-2 gas sensor has high affectability to LPG, Propane and Hydrogen, correspondingly could be utilized to Methane and other ignitable steam, it is adequately and reasonable for various application. Sensor is risky to burnable gas and smoke. Smoke sensor is given 5 volt to control it. Smoke sensor shows smoke by the voltage that it yields .More smoke more yield. A potentiometer is given to change the affectability. Regardless, when smoke exist sensor gives a direct resistive yield subject to centralization of smoke. The circuit has a moreover sizzling. Force is given to radiator by VCC and GND from control supply. The circuit has a variable resistor. The opposition over the pin relies on the smoke in air in the sensor. The limitation will be chopped down if the substance is more. What's more, voltage is reached out between the sensor and weight resistor.

RELAY:

Relays are the essential security comparatively as exchanging contraptions by a long shot a large portion of the control strategies or device. The entirety of the trades reacts to in any occasion one electrical aggregate like voltage or stream to such an extent, that they open or close the contacts or circuits.

A hand-off is an exchanging contraption as it tries to separate or change the condition of an electric circuit starting with one state then onto the accompanying.

mishap along the area to be send. Every one of the information get from the controller has refreshed to cloud so the proprietor can be screen too control alongside notice message send.

VI. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

HELMET SECTION:

Table 1: MQ2 Gas Sensor output

Distance(mm)	Response timemsec
10	0.01
20	0.02
30	0.04
40	2
50	2.5
60	2.5
70	3
80	5
90	7
100	7
110	7.5
120	8
130	8

Table 2: Gyroscope response output

Angle in degree	Response time msec
30	0.05
90	0.02
180	0.01
270	0.03
360	0.02

VEHICLE SECTION:

IX. CONCLUSION

There are different mishap ID cases. In our work, the exactness and exactness are high, which shows that our proposed framework is precise in observing calamities by utilizing the vibration, load checking, MEMEs and high liquor use. The relationship of the parameters for catastrophe ID shows the centrality of the utilization of head protector.

VII. FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

This approach depends on the third contrast in Bone Similar to their plan; we also use Naor Rheingold style PRF and multi straight maps to get the mystery keys and open keys to O (log N) parts, figuratively speaking. Another general bearing is to consider secure system coding in a structure where on a very basic level authentic security or insurance from computationally obliged foes is required.

VIII. RESULT

In this venture, the employments of IOT with head protector are, it can give the framework can counteract the utilization of liquor while riding. Vital move to be made at the hour of

REFERENCE

1. SayanTapadar, Arnab Kumar Saha, Dr. Himadri Nath Saha, Shinjini Ray, "Fiasco and Alcohol Detection in Bluetooth empowered Smart Helmets for Motorbikes"978-1-5386-4649-6/18/\$31.00 ©2018 IEEE.
2. Ms. Rekha. M, Ms. Bharathi. K, Ms. Cynthia, "Drive incapacitated Detection System" © 2014-17, IJIRAE.
3. P. THARANGAI THAMIL, S. VANITHA "Concentrate on Rash Driving Detection Using Acceleration and Orientation Sensors" ISSN 2278 – 0882 Volume 4, Issue 3, March 2015.
4. Amrutha Madhusan, Lavanya Viswanathan, Vaishnavi Ravindran, Dr. ShantaRangaswamy," A study on Road Accident Detection and Reporting" Volume 7, Issue 4, April-2016.
5. C. Prabha, R.Sunitha , R.Anitha,"Automatic Vehicle Accident Detection and Messaging System Using GSM and GPS Modem", Vol. 3, Issue 7, July 2014 DOI: 10.15662/ijareeie.2014.0307062.